

Enhancing Reliability in Heavy Duty Autonomous Mobile Machines Through Fault Tolerant Edge Computing

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Abstract This paper presents a novel fault-tolerant edge computing architecture for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines in industrial environments. The proposed system integrates two virtual machine hosts with a circular topology of four Ethernet switches, ensuring network resilience and operational continuity. A key feature is the implementation of automatic takeover protocols, enabling seamless transition between hosts during hardware failures. The network infrastructure leverages Rapid Spanning Tree Protocol (RSTP) and additional loop protection mechanisms to maintain stability and achieve rapid fault recovery. Virtual machines running Ubuntu Linux or FreeBSD are strategically deployed to handle specific tasks with critical services replicated for enhanced reliability. The system incorporates advanced data management through a PostgreSQL database with master-slave replication. Comprehensive fault tolerance mechanisms, including redundant connections and graceful degradation capabilities, ensure robust performance in challenging industrial settings. This architecture significantly enhances the reliability and autonomy of heavy-duty mobile machines, addressing the critical need for uninterrupted operation in industrial automation applications.

Keywords Edge computing · Graceful degradation · Autonomous mobile machine · Fault tolerance · High availability

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The growth of complex, autonomous, heavy-duty mobile machines in industrial environments has necessitated robust, reliable computing systems capable of managing mission-critical operations [7, 8]. These machines, such as mining equipment like excavators and loaders, operate in challenging environments characterized by extreme conditions [5]. Operating conditions include, for example:

- Underground mines with complex tunnel networks
- GNSS denied environments and limited external network connectivity
- Harsh conditions, including extreme temperatures, dust, and mist
- Continuous operation cycles of 16–24 h per day.

Traditionally, these machines have been operated by onboard human drivers, utilizing hydraulic actuators and control systems built around CAN-bus technology. They incorporate a limited number of sensors for essential surveillance and operational monitoring. However, the increasing demand for efficiency and safety has driven the development of more autonomous capabilities [2]. The system proposed in this paper does not eliminate the possibility of human operation but enhances it, allowing for various levels of autonomy as operational needs dictate. This flexibility is crucial in adapting to different scenarios within industrial settings. A promising solution for these applications has emerged from edge computing, moving computational resources closer to the origin of data [1, 11]. In edge computing, data is processed near its origin, thus conserving bandwidth, reducing latency, and enhancing real-time decision-making capabilities [10]. Nevertheless, the distributed essence of edge computing raises challenges in ensuring system reliability and fault tolerance, particularly in the context of heavy-duty mobile machines operating in remote and harsh environments.

1.2 Problem Statement

Reliability is paramount for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines operating in challenging, remote environments. The central problem lies in the vulnerability of edge computing systems to unexpected failures, potentially compromising continuous operation [5, 12]. Challenges include:

- Hardware failures in remote locations
- Network instability and intermittent connectivity
- Limited computational resources at the edge
- Diverse failure modes in mobile industrial settings
- Need for graceful degradation and rapid recovery without manual intervention.

1.3 Objective

This research aims to develop and implement a robust, fault-tolerant edge computing architecture for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines while advancing the theoretical understanding of fault tolerance in mobile edge computing environments. The primary objectives are:

1. To develop a scalable and adaptable fault-tolerant edge computing architecture that enhances reliability and ensures continuous operation of autonomous mobile machines in challenging industrial environments.
2. To implement comprehensive fault management mechanisms, including automatic fault detection, isolation, recovery, and graceful degradation strategies.
3. To study IT infrastructure technologies not commonly used inside mobile machines but which might be beneficial for improving reliability.
4. To study the trade-offs between system complexity, fault tolerance, and operational efficiency in the context of autonomous mobile machines.

By achieving these objectives, we aim to make mobile industrial automation more efficient, safer, and reliable in harsh environments, eventually improving productivity and safety across various industries.

2 System Architecture

2.1 Overview

The fault-tolerant edge computing architecture for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines integrates redundancy, distributed processing, and intelligent fault management. At its core, a dual-host virtual machine (VM) configuration ensures high availability and resilience against hardware failures.

This configuration comprises two computing nodes capable of hosting multiple VMs, working in tandem to share computational load and provide failover capabilities. The virtualization layer enables efficient resource utilization and process isolation, enhancing performance and security.

Four Ethernet switches in a circular topology connect the VM hosts, maintaining network connectivity despite potential link failures and further connecting the hosts to sensors and actuators crucial for the machine's operations. These layer 2 switches provide some layer 3 features to assist advanced management and control functions. Industrial features like RSTP allow quick network reconfiguration, minimizing downtime. Connections are visualized in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Network architecture of the robust control system

Automatic takeover protocols enable a seamless transition of operations to the surviving host in case of failure. The architecture incorporates distributed data management techniques to ensure consistency across the system, employing consensus algorithms and distributed storage solutions to maintain data integrity during intermittent network connectivity.

The system includes mechanisms for graceful degradation, prioritizing critical functions when resources are constrained or components fail. This ensures uninterrupted essential operations while less critical tasks are suspended or run at reduced capacity.

The architecture designed for scalability and adaptability, can accommodate additional nodes as needed, and evolves to meet increasing computational demands or provide higher levels of redundancy for critical applications.

In conclusion, this fault-tolerant edge computing architecture represents a comprehensive approach to ensuring reliability and performance in heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines. Combining redundant hardware, intelligent software protocols, and adaptive resource management provides a robust platform capable of withstanding various failure scenarios while maintaining critical functions in challenging mobile industrial environments.

2.2 *Virtual Machine Hosts*

The fault-tolerant edge computing architecture utilizes dual high-performance VMs hosts as its computational core. These industrial-grade servers are engineered to operate reliably in harsh industrial environments, withstanding vibrations, temperature extremes, and other environmental stressors.

Each host employs a specialized hypervisor based on the Proxmox Virtual Environment, which is well-fitted for edge computing. This configuration allows the deployment of over 30 VMs across both hosts, each dedicated to specific autonomous machine operations. The VMs operate Ubuntu Linux or FreeBSD, selected for their stability, security features, and suitability for the specific task.

The dual-host setup is integral to the system's fault tolerance strategy. Under normal conditions, the computational load is balanced between hosts. In the event of host failure, critical VMs are quickly migrated or restarted on the surviving host, a process managed by health monitoring algorithms.

A PostgreSQL database system, configured in a master-slave replication setup, ensures data consistency and seamless failover. This centralized data store manages operational data, sensor readings, machine states, and configuration information.

The architecture is designed for scalability, allowing integration of additional hosts for increased complexity or redundancy, thus accommodating evolving computational demands in mobile industrial automation applications.

2.3 Virtual Machines

The fault-tolerant edge computing architecture strategically deploys over thirty VMs across two hosts. Dynamic resource allocation optimizes performance by configuring VMs with varying resource allocations based on their roles, ensuring optimal performance for each function. For instance, VMs responsible for real-time sensor data processing receive higher CPU and memory allocations to ensure low-latency performance, while less time-sensitive tasks are allocated fewer resources.

Each VM operates in an isolated environment, enhancing overall system security and preventing resource contention between services. The isolation is vital for the integrity of critical processes and for containing potential issues within individual VMs. Critical services run on VMs configured for real-time replication between hosts to ensure high availability, enabling rapid failover in case of host failure and minimizing downtime. VM checkpointing for critical VMs further enhances fault tolerance, allowing quick rollback to known good states during software failures or data corruption.

The system includes a sophisticated resource allocation algorithm that supports graceful degradation, dynamically adjusting VM priorities and resources in response to hardware failures or extreme processing loads. This approach ensures the autonomous machine can operate safely and effectively, even under constrained resources. Integrating a centralized PostgreSQL database keeps data consistent throughout the system and helps with fault tolerance and failover strategies. It also allows for real-time data sharing between the different parts of the autonomous system.

This VM-based approach, emphasizing fault tolerance and graceful degradation, is the key to achieving the high reliability and performance required for autonomous operations in challenging industrial environments. The VM architecture's flexibility

makes it possible to adapt to changing conditions and maintain operational continuity even in the case of hardware malfunction or resource constraints, making it well-suited for the demands of heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines.

2.4 *Virtual Machine Versus Container*

The comparison between complete VMs and containers is a topic of great interest in information technology. Containers, often managed by systems like Docker, offer lightweight solutions for rapid deployment and scalability. They encapsulate applications and dependencies into mostly isolated packages that share the kernel of the host operating system, resulting in lower utilization of resources but inducing potential security vulnerabilities due to this shared architecture.

In contrast, VMs provide robust isolation by encapsulating entire guest operating systems at the hardware level through hypervisors. This approach creates firm security boundaries, crucial for applications requiring stringent compliance or legacy systems unsuitable for containerization. VMs offer greater flexibility in operating system choice, benefiting applications tied to specific OS versions or environments requiring replication.

VMs demonstrate superior fault tolerance and resilience, allowing seamless migration between hosts during failures. They leverage established management tools and security controls, providing administrators with familiar frameworks for virtualized environments. While containers may initiate faster, VMs offer more consistent and predictable performance profiles, especially for resource-intensive applications. Additionally, VMs provide mature, feature-rich, persistent storage options, which are advantageous for long-term data retention.

In the context of fault-tolerant edge computing for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines, VMs are preferable due to their strong isolation, diverse OS support, resource allocation flexibility, and performance predictability. The mature fault tolerance mechanisms of VMs, such as live migration and checkpointing, are essential for maintaining continuous operation in mobile industrial settings. Furthermore, VMs' persistent storage capabilities better suit robust data management and long-term retention needs critical for autonomous machine learning and system diagnostics.

While containers excel in agility and efficiency, VMs remain indispensable when strong isolation, diverse OS support, resource-intensive applications, and established management practices are required. The choice between containers and VMs ultimately depends on specific application needs and organizational requirements. However, VMs' advantages in security, flexibility, fault tolerance, performance consistency, and persistent storage make them crucial tools for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machine applications.

2.5 *Network Switches*

The proposed fault-tolerant edge computing system for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines utilizes a network infrastructure comprising four Teltonika TSW202 industrial-grade Ethernet switches. The key innovation is how these technologies are applied and integrated to enhance reliability in mobile industrial environments.

A circular topology, atypical in mobile machinery, is implemented to maintain network integrity in harsh, high-vibration environments. Each switch maintains dedicated connections to its adjacent peers, creating redundant pathways essential for continuous operation during environmental stresses.

An advanced configuration of the RSTP (IEEE 802.1AC) manages this loop topology effectively [4]. Switch-to-switch uplink ports are configured with point-to-point link type settings and automatic cost calculations based on link speed, allowing quick adaptation to dynamic conditions. The implementation achieves instant failure detection in case of link failure and less than 3 seconds to adapt to the failure when using RSTP hello-time of 1 s.

This approach addresses the critical need for uninterrupted operation in mobile industrial automation applications, enhancing the reliability and autonomy of heavy-duty mobile machines.

2.6 *Sensors and Actuators*

Integrating sensors and actuators in heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines presents challenges distinct from stationary industrial systems. Our approach focuses on improving the reliability and fault tolerance of these critical components, which operate under extreme conditions and constant motion. Unlike stationary industrial systems executing single tasks, these machines operate in multi-modal configurations, requiring adaptive and robust sensor-actuator networks.

We implement a multi-layered sensor redundancy strategy, employing diverse sensing modalities to measure identical parameters. This redundancy is crucial in mobile environments prone to sensor failure due to vibration, shock, or environmental factors. For instance, our system combines LiDAR, radar, and camera data for obstacle detection, ensuring reliable environmental perception even if one sensor type fails.

Our actuator control system utilizes a distributed architecture where control units can operate independently if isolated from the central system. This design ensures that critical functions remain operational during partial system failures.

We have developed a novel predictive maintenance approach for sensors and actuators in mobile environments. The system detects signs of potential failures by

monitoring performance characteristics and environmental conditions. This proactive approach is useful for mobile machinery; unexpected faults between regular maintenance breaks often disrupt continuous operation.

Our fault-tolerant design considers the practical limitations of implementing a complete backup system in mobile machinery while focusing on improving availability and implementing software-based fault detection and compensation mechanisms. This balanced approach improves system resilience without increasing the costs and compromising economic feasibility.

3 Fault Tolerance Mechanisms

3.1 Automatic Takeover

The fault-tolerant edge computing system for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines incorporates an automatic takeover mechanism utilizing a Proxmox High Availability (HA) cluster. The Proxmox HA cluster has been adapted for mobile settings through a three-node configuration: two active nodes on the machine and a third quorum device in a vehicle-mounted unit. This configuration maintains quorum and prevents split-brain scenarios during malfunction.

The implementation leverages Proxmox's live migration capabilities that proactively initiate VM migrations based on predictive analysis of machine movement and anticipated network conditions. This approach significantly reduces the risk of service interruptions during critical operations.

3.2 Redundant Connections

The circular network topology forms the basis for a robust redundancy strategy explicitly designed for mobile industrial environments. VM hosts are multi-homed, connected to multiple switches, maintaining network resilience despite the frequent vibrations and jolts that heavy machinery experiences. Link aggregation techniques have been adapted to the mobile context. A single logical link is formed by combining similar physical links to provide seamless failover and increase bandwidth in harsh operational conditions. This redundancy approach extends to sensors and actuators, often overlooked in less mobile-focused systems. Connecting these devices to multiple switches ensures data transmission to processing units through alternative paths in case of connection failures due to machine movement or environmental factors.

3.3 Protocols

Various protocols have been adapted to enhance fault tolerance in the challenging conditions faced by heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines. The RSTP implementation has been optimized for swift network reconfiguration during frequent link failures common in mobile environments. For virtual machine hosts running Proxmox, the Corosync Cluster Engine has been customized to maintain cluster integrity in high-vibration and electromagnetically noisy environments. Modifications allow frequent heartbeat messages and tolerant quorum calculations, which are crucial for maintaining an accurate cluster state in mobile settings. At the application level, protocols such as Fast DDS with ROS2 and MQTT have been enhanced with secondary distribution services and brokers, providing essential redundancies for maintaining messaging operations despite network instabilities typical in mobile industrial settings.

4 Reliability Analysis

This section presents an overview of the reliability calculations and methodologies for analyzing the fault-tolerant edge computing system designed for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines.

The system's reliability is modeled using a hybrid series-parallel approach. This method accounts for the complex interdependencies between components and sub-systems. The overall system reliability is calculated for different operational modes, reflecting the system's ability to adapt to various tasks and conditions.

1. For components in parallel:

$$R_{\text{parallel}} = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - R_i) \quad (1)$$

where R_i is the reliability of the i -th component.

2. For components in series:

$$R_{\text{series}} = \prod_{i=1}^n R_i \quad (2)$$

3. Overall system reliability:

$$R_{\text{system}} = R_{\text{series}} \times R_{\text{parallel}} \quad (3)$$

Table 1 shows individual component reliability over 10 years. These values are used as inputs for the above calculations. The table shows the components of the

Table 1 Reliability of traditional system components

Subsystem	Reliability
PLC	0.90
Communication bus	0.90
Software	0.90
24 V power	0.90
Hydraulics	1.00
Traditional sensors	1.00
Whole system	0.66

The bold values indicate the reliability of overall system.

Table 2 Reliability of new system components

Component	Reliability	Amount	P/S	Total reliability
Computer	0.90	2	2P	0.99
Communication bus	0.90	2	2P	0.99
Software with autorecovery	0.90	2	2P	0.99
Hydraulics	1.00			1.00
Traditional sensor	1.00			1.00
24 V power	0.90	2	2P	0.99
Supportive sensor	0.90	8	8S	0.43
Sensor for work and drive	0.90	12	12S	0.28
Sensor for safety	0.90	8	2P4S	0.96
Whole system				0.11

The bold values indicate the reliability of overall system.

traditional system for reference, which follows a pure series configuration. For comparability, every subsystem is claimed to have a reliability of 0.9 over ten years. For the same reason, Hydraulics and sensors, which will stay the same, are claimed to have a reliability of 1.0.

The traditional system might look superior when comparing it to the new one. As seen in Table 2, overall reliability decreases quickly when the number of subsystems increases. This happens even though some subsystems are doubled, allowing graceful degradation.

In practice, the new system's reliability varies across different operational modes due to the engagement of different components and subsystems. Several frameworks exist to classify autonomy levels in the development of autonomous mobile machines. The Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) International's J3016 standard, initially developed for on-road vehicles, has been widely adopted and adapted for off-road and mining applications. This framework defines six levels of driving automation, from 0 (no automation) to 5 (full automation), as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 SAE levels of driving automation

Level	Description
0	No automation
1	Driver assistance
2	Partial automation
3	Conditional automation
4	High automation
5	Full automation

The SAE levels provide a standardized way to describe the capabilities of autonomous systems, facilitating communication between developers, regulators, and end-users [9]. In the context of mining mobile mining equipment, these levels help define the degree of human intervention required and the extent of the machine’s decision-making capabilities. In our work, we primarily reference the SAE levels when discussing the autonomy capabilities of mobile machines. The autonomous mobile machine system described here operates in five modes, each tailored to specific operational requirements and operating under varying SAE levels.

Salvage mode bypasses standard safety protocols and autonomy features, allowing emergency operations or recovery in extreme situations. It relies solely on traditional sensors and a minimal control system, without utilizing any new or advanced sensor technologies, to ensure basic functionality in critical scenarios. This is clearly SAE level 0.

Human operator mode is the traditional system with enhanced safety features. This mode relies on direct human control while maintaining advanced safety measures. It incorporates new sensor technologies specifically designed to improve safety, providing operators with enhanced awareness of the machine’s environment and potential hazards. The safety features are comparable to emergency braking and blind spot warnings in the car; thus, it operates at SAE level 0.

Augmented human operator mode builds upon the human operator mode. This configuration incorporates augmented reality technologies to enhance the operator’s situational awareness and decision-making capabilities. Additionally, it utilizes supportive sensors for work-related tasks. While these supportive sensors may introduce a degree of complexity that could potentially decrease overall system reliability, it is important to note that they are not critical for basic operation. The system can continue to function safely even if these supportive sensors fail. These functions are comparable to lane centering in the car. These functions raise the SAE level to 1.

Work mode focuses on on-spot tasks, activating components and systems specific to stationary work operations and optimizing efficiency for localized tasks. It represents a partially autonomous configuration that builds upon the augmented human operator mode. In addition to the existing sensor array, this mode utilizes four critical extra sensors to enhance its autonomous capabilities for specific work-related operations. These additional sensors are essential for the autonomous functions in

Table 4 Reliability across different operational modes

Operational mode	SAE	Reliability	Description
Salvage	0	0.96	Bypass safety and autonomy
Operator	0	0.82	Traditional system, safety
Augmented operator	1	0.54	Traditional system, safety, augmented reality
Work	2	0.43	Stationary work systems
Driving and SLAM	4	0.35	Autonomous driving

this mode, distinguishing it from the previous modes in terms of both capability and operational requirements. SAE level is about 2.

Driving and SLAM mode represent the most autonomous operating mode of the system. It heavily utilizes sensor arrays and advanced computational systems for autonomous navigation and environment mapping, employing Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) techniques. This mode incorporates 8 critical sensors, significantly enhancing its ability to perceive and interpret complex environments. The high number of critical sensors underscores the sophisticated level of autonomy achieved in this mode, enabling the machine to navigate and operate with minimal human intervention in dynamic industrial settings.

Table 4 shows the reliability and the level of autonomy for each operational mode. Reliability value is calculated using Eqs. 1–3 with values from Table 2. It highlights the evident fact that as the autonomy level of a system increases, the system's complexity naturally grows, leading to a decrease in overall reliability. To mitigate this, subsystems needed for safe human operations are connected in parallel, unlike serial connections, which have lower reliability since one component malfunctioning would lead to the loss of the entire system.

Critical components in the system, such as computer systems and sensors, are essential and shared across most operational modes. To ensure the reliability of these components, the system incorporates redundancy. This is reflected in the calculations where the reliability of these components is significantly improved. For instance, the reliability of two computers is calculated as:

$$R_{\text{one_computer}} = 0.9 \quad (4)$$

$$R_{\text{two_computers}} = 1 - (1 - R_{\text{one_computer}})^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.9)^2 = 0.99 \quad (5)$$

This demonstrates how incorporating redundancy, in this case using two computers, dramatically improves reliability from 90 to 99%. With redundancy, the system

can continue operating even if one computer fails, which is crucial for maintaining performance across different modes.

The system's ability to operate in different modes with varying levels of reliability indicates a design philosophy of graceful degradation. This is particularly notable in the "salvage" mode, where the system can operate with minimal functionality, bypassing safety systems if necessary.

While not explicitly shown in the table, the reliability calculations implicitly consider the results of an FMEA. This is evident in how different components contribute to the reliability of various operational modes. This analysis has at least the following limitations and assumptions.

- Perfect reliability is assumed for hydraulics and traditional sensors, which may not reflect real-world conditions.
- The analysis assumes independence between failure modes of different components, which may not always be the case in a tightly integrated system.
- Environmental factors and their impact on component reliability are not explicitly accounted for in this model.

The reliability analysis demonstrates the complex interplay between components' reliability and system-level performance across different operational modes. While the new system shows improved reliability in some areas, the trade-offs in others highlight the challenges in designing multi-modal autonomous systems. This analysis provides a foundation for future reliability engineering efforts and system optimizations.

5 Upgrading and Reconfiguring

In today's interconnected industrial world, the ability to update, upgrade, and reconfigure autonomous mobile machines is not merely advantageous but essential. The ubiquity of network connectivity, whether local or global, necessitates a proactive approach to system maintenance and enhancement. Our fault-tolerant edge computing architecture, leveraging high-level operating systems, provides a robust foundation for addressing these requirements.

The proposed architecture offers several key advantages over traditional systems. Primarily, it enables Over-the-Air (OTA) updates, significantly reducing downtime and maintenance costs. The modular software architecture facilitates targeted upgrades and re-configurations without system-wide disruptions. Virtualization allows for isolated testing of updates before full deployment, enhancing system stability. Moreover, high-level operating systems provide robust security features and regular patches against emerging threats.

Traditional systems, often reliant on Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) and rigid Communication Area Network (CAN) protocols, present significant challenges in upgrading and reconfiguring. These systems typically require on-site interventions, leading to extended downtime and increased operational costs. In contrast, our

architecture's flexibility allows for rapid adaptation to changing demands and swift responses to security vulnerabilities.

Quickly deploying security patches is crucial in an era of evolving cyber threats. Our system's network-centric design, coupled with high-level operating systems, enables prompt responses to identified vulnerabilities. This agility in security management is vital for autonomous mobile machines operating in diverse and potentially hostile environments [5].

Mobile industrial environments are dynamic, with evolving operational requirements. The proposed architecture's reconfigurability allows for integrating new functionalities and optimizing existing processes without necessitating complete system overhauls. This adaptability ensures that autonomous mobile machines remain at the forefront of technological capabilities, maintaining their operational relevance and efficiency over time [10].

In conclusion, the upgrading and reconfiguring capabilities of our fault-tolerant edge computing architecture represent a significant advancement over traditional systems. By embracing modern, connected technologies, we provide a platform that is more responsive to current needs and well-positioned to adapt to future challenges in mobile industrial automation systems.

6 Results and Discussion

The proposed fault-tolerant edge computing architecture for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines demonstrates significant improvements in reliability and operational flexibility compared to traditional systems. Our analysis reveals several key findings:

Table 4 summarizes the reliability calculations for different operational modes of the system. The results indicate a trade-off between system complexity and reliability as the level of autonomy increases. The result aligns with findings from similar studies in autonomous systems [7].

The system's ability to operate in different modes with varying levels of reliability demonstrates the effective implementation of graceful degradation principles. That is particularly evident in the "salvage" mode, which maintains a high reliability of 0.96 by bypassing non-critical systems.

The redundancy in critical components, such as computer systems and communication buses, significantly enhances system reliability. For instance, the reliability of the computer system improves from 0.90 for a single unit to 0.99 with redundancy.

The circular topology of the network switches, coupled with the implementation of RSTP, provides robust network resilience. In some cases, the proposed system achieves instant failure detection and network reconfiguration within 3 seconds when using an RSTP hello-time of 1 second. This rapid recovery is crucial for maintaining continuous operation in mobile industrial environments, outperforming traditional linear network topology [4].

While the overall system reliability appears lower than a traditional system (0.66 vs. 0.35 for the most complex mode), it is important to note that:

1. The new system offers significantly higher functionality and autonomy levels.
2. The reliability calculation for the new system includes a more comprehensive set of components, reflecting its increased complexity.
3. The system's ability to operate in multiple modes allows for continued operation at reduced functionality levels, which is not captured in a single reliability figure.

The architecture's high-level operating systems and virtualization technologies enable OTA updates and flexible reconfiguration. Those improvements represent a significant advancement over traditional PLC-based systems, aligning with industry trends toward more adaptable and updateable mobile industrial automation systems [5].

The current analysis provides valuable insights, but it has limitations. The assumption of perfect reliability for hydraulics and traditional sensors may not reflect real-world conditions. Additionally, the study assumes independence between failure modes of different components, which may only sometimes hold in tightly integrated systems.

7 Conclusion

Our system's performance can be attributed to several key features:

The circular network topology provides robust redundancy against link failures. The dual-host VM configuration with automatic takeover protocols ensures high availability. Implementing graceful degradation mechanisms allows the system to maintain critical functions even under partial failures. Adapting fault tolerance mechanisms specific for mobile high-vibration environments decreases the risk of physical failure.

While cloud-based systems offer high-computational redundancy, they fall short in scenarios with unreliable network connectivity, a common challenge in mobile industrial environments. Traditional systems, while robust in certain aspects, lack the flexibility and advanced fault tolerance features required for autonomous operations.

In conclusion, our proposed fault-tolerant edge computing architecture demonstrates significant advantages over existing systems, particularly in its ability to maintain operational continuity in the challenging conditions faced by heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines.

7.1 Summary

This paper presents a novel fault-tolerant edge computing architecture for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines operating in challenging industrial environments.

The proposed system addresses critical reliability issues in industrial automation applications, particularly in scenarios with limited network connectivity and harsh operating conditions. Key features of the architecture include:

- A dual-host virtual machine configuration with over 30 VMs, enhancing computational redundancy and fault tolerance.
- A circular network topology utilizing four Ethernet switches, ensuring network resilience.
- Automatic takeover protocols for seamless transitions during hardware failures.
- Implementation of the RSTP for rapid fault recovery.
- A PostgreSQL database with master-slave replication for robust data management.
- Comprehensive fault tolerance mechanisms, including redundant connections and graceful degradation capabilities.

The system's reliability is analyzed across different operational modes, corresponding to various SAE levels of autonomy. The architecture demonstrates improved fault tolerance compared to traditional systems, particularly in maintaining critical functions during partial failures. The paper also discusses the system's upgradeability and reconfigurability, highlighting advantages over traditional PLC-based systems in terms of OTA updates and security patch deployment. This research enhances the reliability and autonomy of heavy-duty mobile machines in industrial settings, addressing the growing demand for robust, autonomous operations in challenging environments.

7.2 Future Work

The complexity of the fault-tolerant edge computing system for heavy-duty autonomous mobile machines necessitates advanced reliability analysis techniques. While the current study provides valuable insights, future work should focus on more nuanced approaches to examine the system's complicated behavior under various operational conditions. One promising future research direction is using Multi-State System (MSS) Reliability Analysis methods. Unlike traditional binary (functioning/failed) reliability models, MSS methods can account for systems with multiple performance levels [6]. This approach is particularly relevant for our system, which exhibits graceful degradation and can operate in various modes with different levels of functionality and reliability. The application of MSS methods could provide several benefits:

1. More accurate representation of system behavior, accounting for partial failures and degraded performance states.
2. Better modeling of the system's ability to transition between operational modes in response to component failures or environmental conditions.
3. Enhanced understanding of the system's resilience and capacity to maintain critical functions under diverse failure scenarios.

4. Improved decision-making for maintenance scheduling and resource allocation based on a more granular understanding of system states.

This approach would allow for a more refined analysis of the system's reliability across its various operational modes and provide deeper insights into its fault-tolerant capabilities. Such analysis could inform future design iterations and optimization strategies, ultimately enhancing the system's overall performance and reliability in mobile industrial environments.

Cybersecurity is critical for future research in distributed edge computing systems, particularly for autonomous mobile machines that operate near people and other machines. As these systems become more interconnected and rely heavily on data exchange, they become increasingly vulnerable to cyber threats and face heightened challenges in maintaining operational reliability and physical safety [3].

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